

تکافل اور انشورنس ایک تقابلی جائزہ

TAKAFUL AND INSURANCE – A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Insurance is one of the key parts in current economic system of the world. But majority of Islamic scholars declare it void according to the Islamic teachings. The main reason for declaring insurance void is existence of Riba & Gharar in it according the arguments of the shariah scholars. As the importance of insurance does not need to be proved Takaful was presented as its alternate by many Islamic jurists in the last century. But there is considerable number of Muslim scholars who think that Takafaul is also void because it is similar to the system of conventional insurance. This article aims to study the similarities and differences of insurance and Takaful systems and to analyze the differences in the light of Islamic teachings.

Keywords: Insurance, Takaful, Islamic Insurance, Shariah, Islamic Teaching.

کلیدی الفاظ: انشورنس، تکافل، اسلامی انشورنس، شریعہ، اسلامی تعلیمات۔

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